

Supplementary material – data extraction form

Post-discharge Care Interventions to Support Patient Recovery after Elective Degenerative Spine Surgery – a systematic review

Lorenzen MD, Wickstrøm LA, Andersen MØ, Carreon LY, Clemensen J, and Frandsen TF

This data extraction form is developed from Cochrane’s “Data collection form for intervention reviews: RCTs and non-RCTs” (1)

General Information

Date form completed (<i>dd/mm/yyyy</i>)	26-09-2022		
Name/ID of person extracting data	MDL		
Author(s)	He, Q. et al.		
Country	China		
Publication year	2021		
Title of article	Effect of continuous nursing based on wechat platform on postoperative rehabilitation of patients with lumbar disc herniation		
Title of journal	Jpn J Nurs Sci		
Volume 18	Issue e12382	Pages 1-7	
Publication type (<i>e.g. full report, abstract, letter</i>)	Scientific article		

Study eligibility

Study Characteristics	Eligibility criteria <i>There are no restrictions on the types of study.</i>				Location in text or source (<i>pg & %/fig/table/other</i>)
		Yes	No	Unclear	
Type of study	Randomised Controlled Trial	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Abstract, p. 2
	Quasi-randomised Controlled Trial	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Controlled Before and After Study	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Other design (specify):	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Participants	Patients with LDH who underwent surgery	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	p. 2
Types of intervention	Continuous nursing based on the wechat platform	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	p. 2
Types of comparison	Routine continuous nursing	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	p. 2

Types of outcome measures	Function disability /status, quality of life, nerve function, patients' compliance, and effectiveness	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	p. 2-3
INCLUDE <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		EXCLUDE <input type="checkbox"/>			

Characteristics of included studies

Methods

	Descriptions as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Aim of study (e.g. efficacy, equivalence, pragmatic)	To investigate whether continuous nursing based on wechat platform could increase patients' compliance and exercise frequency, and provide a reference for the clinic	p. 2
Design (e.g. parallel, crossover, non-RCT)	Randomized controlled trial	Abstract + p. 2
Start date	March 2, 2016	Abstract + p. 2
End date	June 23, 2018	Abstract + p. 2
Ethical approval needed/ obtained for study	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Unclear The ethics committee of Suzhou BenQ Medical Center approved this study	p. 2

Participants

	Description <i>Include comparative information for each intervention or comparison group if available</i>	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Setting (including location and social context)	Suzhou BenQ Medical Center	p. 2
Inclusion criteria	Inclusion criteria were: (a) meeting the surgery indication and receiving surgery for the first time; (b) ability to use the wechat on a mobile phone, which refers to owning a smartphone and the ability to log in to wechat, read and reply to wechat content, and read push content all by themselves; (c) willing to join in the survey and sign the informed consent.	p. 2
Exclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria were: (a) receiving conservative treatments; (b) suspected or confirmed tumors of lumbar spine and spinal canal; (c) suffering serious heart, brain, lung and kidney diseases; (d) unwilling to join in the survey.	p. 2

Informed consent obtained	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Unclear	p. 2
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Intervention group

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Group name	Study group	p. 2
No. randomised to group (specify whether no. people or clusters)	N=47 (M:25, F:22) Mean age: 46.0	p. 2, 3 p. 3 table 1
Description (include sufficient detail for replication, e.g. content, dose, components)	In the study group, in addition to routine continuous nursing, patients received continuous nursing based on the wechat platform. Specifically, a wechat group named “postoperative group of patients with LDH” was established. The members of the group included doctors, nurses, patients and their families. The patients in the study group and their families were invited to join the group at the time of discharge. In order to help the patients to understand, functional exercise methods that sometimes could be professional were presented in the form of texts, pictures and videos by the nurses in the wechat group every day. Their families were asked to supervise them to learn and complete the corresponding training, and upload the training video to the wechat group at least once a week in order to confirm the patients were learning and training. Further, the doctors and nurses in the wechat group were required to guide the patients and answer their doubts and those of family members online. The intervention lasted for 3 months.	p. 2

Control group

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Group name	Control group	p. 2
No. randomised to group (specify whether no. people or clusters)	N=48 (M:27, F:21) Mean age	p. 2, 3 p. 3 table 1
Description (include sufficient detail for replication, e.g. content, dose, components)	Routine continuous nursing (pre-discharge education, time for further consultation, answering related questions about LDH, telephone follow-up every 2 weeks after discharge)	p. 2

Outcomes

Outcome 1

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Outcome name	Function disability /status	p. 2,3,4,5
Outcome definition (<i>with diagnostic criteria if relevant</i>)	Oswestry Disability Index (ODI) Favors intervention	p. 2,3,4,5

Outcome 2

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Outcome name	Quality of life	p. 2,3,4,5
Outcome definition (<i>with diagnostic criteria if relevant</i>)	36-item Short Form Survey (SF-36) Favors intervention	p. 2,3,4,5

Outcome 3

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Outcome name	Nerve function	p. 2,3,4,5
Outcome definition (<i>with diagnostic criteria if relevant</i>)	Japanese Orthopedics Associaton (JOA) score	p. 2,3,4,5

Outcome 4

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Outcome name	Patients' compliance	p. 2,3,4,5
Outcome definition (<i>with diagnostic criteria if relevant</i>)	Compliance rate = (full compliance + partial compliance)/total x 100%	p. 2,3,4,5

Outcome 5

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Outcome name	Effectiveness	p. 2,3,4,5
Outcome definition (<i>with diagnostic criteria if relevant</i>)	Effective rate = (completely effective + effective)/total x 100%	p. 2,3,4,5

Follow up

Follow up	3 months	p. 5, table 3-5
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Conclusion

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Conclusion	<p>There were 48 patients in the control group and 47 patients in the study group. The results showed that the compliance rate of the study group was 89.36%, significantly higher than that of the control group (60.42%). The effective rate of the study group was 95.74%, significantly higher than that of the control group (81.25%). Further, continuous nursing based on wechat platform brought more obvious improvement in the SF-36 scores as well as the JOA score and ODI.</p> <p>Conclusion: The compliance rate and the effectiveness rate of patients received continuous nursing based on wechat platform were higher than those of patients who received routine continuous nursing, which further brought more obvious improvement in the quality of life as well as the JOA scores and ODI.</p>	p. 3,4,5,6

References

1. Cochrane. Data collection form for intervention reviews for RCTs and non-RCTs - template [Internet]. The Cochrane Collaboration. 2022 [cited 2022 Sep 15]. Available from: <https://dplp.cochrane.org/data-extraction-forms>